

Gas-phase applications of metal hydrides

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Applications of metal hydrides (MHs) utilise a reversible interaction of a hydride-forming metal/alloy, or intermetallic compound with hydrogen. The reversible process of formation/decomposition of the MH involves two mechanisms. The first one (Eq. 1) is the interaction of the parent metal/intermetallic compound with hydrogen gas while the second (Eq. 2) is electrochemical hydrogenation of the metal (or hydride decomposition) in an electrolyte, e.g., aqueous alkaline solution:

where M is hydride-forming metal (intermetallic); Q is heat released during hydride formation or absorbed during its decomposition; the indexes *s*, *g* and *l* correspond to solid, gas and liquid phases, respectively. Both reactions are reversible, so it is possible to change their direction by a small changes of the external conditions (temperature and hydrogen pressure for Eq. 1; electrode potential and temperature for Eq. 2).

Accordingly, the applications of MHs can be generally classified as the gas-phase (Eq. 1) and electrochemical (Eq. 2) ones [1–3]. The latter include NiMH batteries; air – MH batteries and fuel cells and are subject of the separate considerations [4,5].

This presentation overviews the gas-phase applications of the interstitial/metallic hydrides that utilise the following unique features of the hydrogenation/dehydrogenation reaction (Eq. 1):

- Host metal/alloy matrix accommodates H atoms in the interstitial sites;
- Volume density of the accommodated H atoms 1.5–2.0 times exceeds the one for the liquid H₂;
- Fast and reversible hydrogen uptake and release;
- Extremely wide ranges of the operating temperatures (from <0 to >300°C) and hydrogen pressures (from <1 mbar to >1 kbar) depending on the alloy's composition;
- Significant heat effects, Q, which can vary between <25 and >70 kJ/mol H₂ depending on the alloy's composition;
- 100% selectivity towards H₂;

- Significant volume change of the host metal upon hydrogenation/dehydrogenation (dilatation effects);
- The effects associated with non-equilibrium state of the gas phase when hydrogenation/dehydrogenation reaction takes place, including high catalytic activity of the MH in the hydrogen transfer reactions.

The gas-phase applications of the MHs include but are not limited by the following ones:

- Safe, compact and technologically flexible hydrogen storage;
- Thermally-driven hydrogen compression without moving parts;
- Efficient heat management (refrigeration, heat storage, upgrade and conversion) with a possibility to utilise low-potential heat (T<150°C);
- Hydrogen separation and purification in 1–2 stages at near-ambient conditions;
- Hydrogen getters and sources of low-pressure hydrogen and its heavy isotopes;
- Powder metallurgy including HDDR and hydride combustion synthesis;
- Various catalytic processes.

Most of the MH applications are very important for energy storage and conversion technologies including hydrogen and fuel cell ones. They allow to combine the processes of compact and safe hydrogen storage and its supply, along with the utilisation of waste heat released during operation of other system components [6].

References

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